

The Feynman Path Integral Variation on Varying Lorentzian Manifolds

O Manor

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Abstract:

By using the new framework of the 8-theory and the two main equations, it is possible to create a new version of the Feynman path integral formulation. The positions are coordinates on the Lorentz manifold, and the paths are amounts of metric curvature caused by arbitrary variations, which vanish into matter. The path with the highest probability of states transition is the path with least scattering, or least curvature. The formulation comes to an agreement with the probability in boson emission. In addition, it is imposing limitations on the Feynman formulation as the metric is a subject to constant variance, and the arbitrary variations themselves vary.

Introduction

In the 8-theory a varying Lorentz manifold is the entity of description. The Lorentz manifold is inserted to an Euler Lagrange equation and by doing so, the main equation of the framework is obtained.

$$s = (M, g) \quad (0)$$

$$L = (s, s', t) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} - \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right) \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Are the conditions, which the framework is demanding to retain a stationary manifold. Those two conditions describe a time invariant acceleration directed from extrunum areas of curvature on the Lorentz manifold. Intersection with the so-called dark energy. In addition, if no data is attainable from the first three terms, it's vividly clear that there is an agreement with Einstein's equivalence principle:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \quad (5)$$

The coupling constant equation was obtained by demanding a stationary manifold to experience net variation, $N(V) = 2\left(V + \frac{1}{2}\right)$; $V \geq 0$; $N(V) \in P$ as P to be is the set of primes and the number one. Those ideas yielded an infinite series, in which each distinct boson has a distinct prime, which is the $N(V)$ value. Even amount of variations vanish,

$$2V = 0.$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (6)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (7)$$

$$N_V = 2\left(V + \frac{1}{2}\right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (9)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (10)$$

The Feynman variation on Lorentz manifold - the objective of this part is to find out what is the probability transition of a boson from initial to final state on the manifold. Bosons are associated with prime amount of net variation $N(V) \rightarrow 2\left(V + \frac{1}{2}\right)$ which propagates as ripples on the manifold, given by a variation of the Laplacian:

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2 M(x)}{\partial^2 g} + \frac{\partial^2 M(y)}{\partial^2 g} + \frac{\partial^2 M(z)}{\partial^2 g} \quad (9)$$

First, we define a manifold $s = (M, g)$ and insert it to an Euler LaGrange equation and an initial state of the manifold $S(0) = (M, g)$.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Then we require the manifold to experience arbitrary variations, which vanish into matter.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

$$\delta g = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

For simplicity of notation, define:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} = K \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} = K' \quad (3.4)$$

$$K \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - K' \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (3.5)$$

Let the arbitrary variations appear all across the matrix on the manifold.

$$\delta g \in M(x, y, z) \quad (3.6)$$

Define a ripple propagation of a boson from an initial point on the manifold to a

Final point.

$$q1 = M(x1, y1, z1) \quad (3.7)$$

$$q2 = M(x2, y2, z2) \quad (3.8)$$

The green arrow is directing the from the initial position of the ripple wave to final Position. The blue dots are the electrons omitting bosons, in that case a photon, marked in yellow. The manifold has arbitrary amount of fermions on it, which get scattered by the initial boson wave and omit a new boson. There are infentially more ways than the above drawing, its vivid. The ripple wave will scatter all the arbitrary variaions, but the highest probability of arrival will be at the path of least curvature.

Each fermion which get scattered omitting a boson with random direction of propagation. the framework has no data regarding the position of the propagation. The more arbitrary Variations getting

scattered, the less probable it is to reach the final position. The following can be analyzed by the equation. The more arbitrary variations in the Path, the more curved the matrix, as there is an acceleration of it outward. The acceleration outward is causing the path to be longer and less linear, and so the time to reach the final position is longer, if only. There is no guarantee a photon will reach the final position in this framework as arbitrary variations created in a random fashion, and in configurations which are not predictable. However, if a photon will reach it will be in the least curved path, or the path with the least fermions getting scattered.

$$P = \int_{q_1(t(i))}^{q_2(t(f))} dq \exp[(S_0) \int_{t(i)}^{t(f)} L(s, s') dt] \quad (10)$$

It's unclear whether (10) is solvable as the arbitrary variations themselves vary their position over time and in addition, arbitrary variations appear in random fashion in this framework. It's given by the first equation. So in a sense we can not sum all the paths if the paths vary at all times. It's a complication of the Feynman result, and at the same time just as beautiful as Feynman's result. But if we ignore the complication, the probability transition should be calculated using (10).

References

- [1] Feynman, R. P. (2005). Space-time approach to non-relativistic quantum mechanics. Feynman's Thesis—A New Approach To Quantum Theory, 71-109.7
- [2] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)